

OPEN Cognitive and transcriptomic effects of Epigallocatechin gallate in fetal alcohol spectrum disorders

Anna Ramos-Triguero^{1,2,3,8}, Marta Astals-Vizcaino^{1,2,4,8}, Elisabet Navarro-Tapia^{1,5}, Melina Veiros^{1,2,3}, Adriana Bastons-Compta¹, Leopoldo Martínez^{3,6}, Vicente Andreu-Fernández^{1,5,7,9}✉ & Óscar García-Algar^{1,2,4,9}

Prenatal alcohol exposure impacts fetal development, leading to Fetal Alcohol Spectrum Disorders (FASD) characterized by cognitive, behavioral, and physical impairments. This pre-post, open-label, non-randomized pilot study explores Epigallocatechin-3-Gallate (EGCG), a potent antioxidant and neuronal plasticity modulator, as a therapeutic intervention for FASD improvement. In a 12-month pilot study, patients with 40 FASD (mean age 10 ± 3 years) received 9 mg/kg/day of EGCG, with outcomes assessed through RNA sequencing and neurocognitive evaluations (WISC-IV, CBCL 6–18, and NEPSY-II). Reduced levels of oxidative stress were observed after 6 and 12 months of treatment with EGCG. Significant neurocognitive improvements were shown after one year of treatment in Perceptual Reasoning Index (PRI) and Working Memory Index (WMI) using the WISC-IV test. CBCL test revealed an improvement in aggressive behavior scores after EGCG treatment. NEPSY-II assessment showed improvements in face memory and delayed face memory. Interestingly, no significant improvements were observed in intelligence quotient, attention, anxiety, or depression, which affect a proportion of individuals diagnosed with FASD. Additionally, EGCG modulates molecular pathways associated with neuroinflammation, immune response, and neurogenesis. This study highlights EGCG as a potential therapeutic candidate to ameliorate cognitive and behavioral deficits in children affected by FASD, revealing potential pathways and biomarkers that contribute to these improvements.

ClinicalTrials.gov identifier: NCT02558933 (registered 22 September 2015).

Keywords Fetal alcohol spectrum disorders (FASD), Epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), Prenatal alcohol exposure (PAE), Neuroinflammation, Cognitive enhancement, Neuropsychology

Alcohol consumption during pregnancy produces significant risks to fetal development, leading to neurodevelopmental disorders known as Fetal Alcohol Spectrum Disorder (FASD). Prenatal alcohol exposure (PAE) damage depends on pregnancy stage, dose, consumption pattern, and genetic susceptibility¹. FASD includes deficits in executive function, learning, memory, general cognition, language, and social skills².

Global prevalence of FASD is 7.7 per 1000 population, with the highest prevalence (19.8 per 1000) in European Regions³. However, PAE and FASD are notably higher in Eastern European Countries (EEC) orphanages, with prevalences ranging from 15% to 68%^{4,5}. In addition, among adopted children from EEC, at least 50% exhibit FASD-related symptoms⁶.

Although molecular mechanisms of FASD are not fully understood, PAE produces high levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS), causing oxidative stress and disrupting critical homeostatic pathways⁷. PAE leads to microcephaly and brain architecture and connectivity alterations⁸. Neuroinflammation mediated by microglia activation plays a key role in these effects, with pathways involving MAPK and Notch signaling⁹. Mitochondrial dysfunction has also emerged as a central contributor to neurodevelopmental impairment. Deficits in ATP

¹Grup de Recerca Infancia i Entorn (GRIE), Institut d'investigacions Biomèdiques August Pi i Sunyer (IDIBAPS), Barcelona, Spain. ²Department de Cirurgia i Especialitats Mèdico-Quirúrgiques, Universitat de Barcelona, Barcelona, Spain. ³Institute for Biomedical Research La Paz (IdiPaz), Madrid, Spain. ⁴Department of Neonatology, Hospital Clínic-Maternitat, ICGON, BCNatal, Barcelona, Spain. ⁵Faculty of Health Sciences, Valencian International University (VIU), Valencia, Spain. ⁶Department of Pediatric Surgery, Hospital Universitario La Paz, Madrid, Spain. ⁷Biosanitary Research Institute, Valencian International University (VIU), Valencia, Spain. ⁸These authors contributed equally to this work: Anna Ramos-Triguero and Marta Astals-Vizcaino. ⁹These authors jointly supervised this work: Vicente Andreu-Fernández and Óscar García-Algar. ✉email: vandreu@universidadviu.com

production and increased mitochondrial ROS generation are reported across neurodevelopmental disorders¹⁰ and have recently been described in FASD models, where prenatal alcohol exposure alters mitochondrial morphology, respiratory chain activity, and redox balance^{11,12}. These mitochondrial deficits exacerbate neuronal vulnerability and may underlie part of the cognitive and behavioral phenotype observed in FASD.

Transcriptomic research is crucial for a comprehensive analysis of gene expression patterns in FASD. Limited transcriptomic studies have reported dysregulated pathways related to cell cycle, neurodevelopment, neuroinflammation, apoptosis, and immune function^{9,13,14}. Additionally, there have been improvements in the investigation of genetic polymorphisms¹⁵ and the use of artificial intelligence for FASD diagnosis¹⁶. However, current research is limited by small sample sizes, lack of longitudinal studies, and variability in diagnostic criteria.

Prevention of FASD relies solely on avoiding alcohol during pregnancy, as no treatments address its neurodevelopmental impairments. Pharmacological treatments target symptoms such as hyperactivity, attention problems, aggressiveness, and anxiety^{17,18}. Efforts to enhance neuronal plasticity, synaptic transmission, and reduce oxidative stress are crucial for long-term cognitive and behavioral improvements. Natural antioxidants, such as epigallocatechin-3-gallate (EGCG), showed potential to address neuronal plasticity dysfunction in Alzheimer's disease and Down syndrome (DS)^{19–21}. EGCG targets the root of neurodevelopmental impairments by enhancing neural communication and reducing ROS. In a randomized clinical trial, De la Torre et al. demonstrated that EGCG combined with cognitive training improved visual recognition memory, inhibitory control, and adaptive behavior in individuals with Down syndrome²¹. Given that FASD and DS share similar dysmorphologies, such as craniofacial defects and DYRK1A and RCAN1 genes dysregulation²², EGCG could potentially improve cognitive performance in FASD. Additionally, EGCG has recently been shown to improve mitochondrial function in vivo. In young children with Down syndrome, decaffeinated EGCG supplementation restored mitochondrial complex I and complex V activity in peripheral cells²³, suggesting that EGCG can modulate bioenergetic deficits relevant to neurodevelopmental disorders, including those observed in FASD.

EGCG, the major polyphenol in green tea, reduces oxidative stress by scavenging radicals, inhibiting lipid-peroxidation, and restoring antioxidant levels²⁴. Green tea has exhibited protective effects against neuroinflammation, immune system, and neural plasticity²⁵.

The objective of this study is to analyze how this antioxidant modifies the transcriptional pattern of global expression in blood samples from patients with FASD and thereby improve cognitive performance, helping to unravel the molecular mechanisms that could contribute to early diagnosis and treatment of this disorder.

Results

The study initially enrolled 89 patients, with 49 exclusions: 23 did not meet inclusion criteria, 10 declined participation, and 16 were taking interfering medications. Of the remaining 40 patients (mean age 10 ± 3 years), 18 met diagnostic criteria for FAS and 22 for partial FAS (pFAS). During follow-up, 7 children dropped out before the 6-month visit, leaving 33 children who completed the 6-month evaluation. Between the 6- and 12-month visits, an additional 9 children were lost to follow-up, resulting in 24 children completing the intervention (Fig. 1; Table 1).

To evaluate EGCG as a therapeutic candidate for FASD, neurocognitive evaluation was performed at baseline ($n = 40$), 6 ($n = 33$), and 12 months ($n = 24$). Oxidative stress status was assessed at baseline and 6 and 12 months. At 12 months, 24 patients completed the treatment. Nevertheless, 12 blood samples were not collected due to pain and non-compliance in children. Of the 12 collected, 4 were excluded for not meeting RNAseq quality criteria.

EGCG improves neurocognitive and behavioral scores in FASD

To assess cognitive improvement, WISC-IV scale was administered at baseline, 6, and 12 months after EGCG treatment (Figs. 2a, Supplementary Table S1). In this test, higher scores reflect better cognitive performance, with values above the *borderline range* representing the average/normal population. 12 months results showed improvement in PRI ($p = 0.002$) and WMI ($p = 0.04$) compared to baseline, with PRI scores moving out of the borderline range, while WMI scores reached the upper end of the borderline threshold.

CBCL neurocognitive assessment compared baseline to 12-month results (Figs. 2b, Supplementary Figure S1, Supplementary Table S2). In this case, higher scores indicate greater behavioral problems, with values in the *borderline/clinical range* reflecting pathology. After 12 months, a significant reduction in Aggressive Behavior score ($p = 0.03$) was observed, with scores stabilizing at the borderline threshold.

NEPSY-II evaluated neuropsychological performance pre- and post-intervention (Fig. 2c, Supplementary Table S3). For this scale, higher scores represent better performance, with higher values reflecting closer alignment to expected developmental levels. Significant improvements after 6 and 12 months were obtained for Memory for Faces (MF, $p = 0.02$, $p = 0.005$), Memory for Faces Delayed (MFD, $p < 0.003$, $p = 0.006$).

EGCG reduces oxidative stress in FASD

In 33 FASD patients (19 males, 14 females) at baseline and after 6 months of treatment, oxidative stress was measured by quantifying MDA and 8-isoprostane. MDA, a byproduct of fatty acid oxidation²⁶, and 8-Isoprostane, ROS-induced metabolite²⁷, decreased by 39% ($p = 0.0017$) and 21% ($p = 0.003$), respectively (Figs. 3a–b). These reductions were maintained at 12 months, where both 8-isoprostane and MDA levels remained significantly lower than baseline, indicating sustained attenuation of lipid peroxidation.

LDH activity, evaluated by NADH/mL*min (Fig. 3c), measured catalyzation of NAD⁺ to NADH. In mitochondrial respiration, NADH donates electrons to Complex I, producing NAD⁺ and O₂⁻ and subsequently H₂O₂ in Complex III, increasing ROS production. A 57% increase in NADH after 6 months, this trend was also shown at 12 months, indicating a significant reduction of oxidative stress ($p < 0.0001$).

These results showed a reduction in oxidative stress markers after 6 and 12 months of EGCG treatment.

Fig. 1. CONSORT Diagram. Flowchart of the study in children with FASD during 12 months.

EGCG modifies FASD transcriptomic profile

RNAseq of blood samples from FASD patients revealed the transcriptomic profile of FASD patients and EGCG treatment effect. PCA confirmed no outliers and clear differences (Supplementary Figure S2) between baseline and 12 months of EGCG treatment.

62,712 expressed genes were detected by comparing 8 FASD patients (4 male, 4 female) at baseline and after 12 months. 6,635 differentially expressed genes (DEG) were identified after EGCG treatment (Fig. 4a), comprising 2,922 downregulated and 3,713 upregulated (Fig. 4b).

Gender ♂ / ♀	N (%)	Diagnosis		Height, cm ± SD	Weight, kg ± SD	BMI ± SD	Age, years ± SD	Min, years	Max, years
		FAS	pFAS						
Male	23 (57.5)	8	15	139.0 ± 15.6	32.1 ± 10.3	16.1 ± 1.8	10 ± 2	7	16
Female	17 (42.5)	10	7	130.9 ± 18.0	30.6 ± 12.0	17.1 ± 2.9	10 ± 3	5	16
Total	40 (100)	18	22	135.5 ± 16.9	31.4 ± 10.9	16.5 ± 2.4	10 ± 3	5	16

Table 1. Distribution by sex, mean height, weight, BMI and age of the FASD participants.

KEGG analysis^{28–30} was performed among genes significantly expressed after EGCG treatment. Enriched pathways can be grouped based on their function (Fig. 4c, Supplementary Table S4), showing significant differences in inflammation-related pathways, such as chemokine signaling, MAPK, PPAR, and immune system pathways, including antigen processing and presentation, phagosome, NOD-like receptor, endocytosis and cytosolic DNA-sensing pathway. Additionally, fatty acid metabolism, encompassing fat digestion and absorption and oxidative stress pathways, such as peroxisome. Other pathways involved were related to skeletal homeostasis, RNA-protein, and carbohydrate metabolism.

Pathways relevant to FASD pathogenesis and EGCG treatment were evaluated. Inflammation-related pathways were analyzed, due to the impairment during brain development³¹, as chemokine, MAPK, and PPAR signaling. KEGG analysis highlighted chemokine signaling as the most enriched pathway after EGCG treatment (Fig. 4c). The identified genes are shown in the Heatmap (Fig. 5a), including PI3KR1 and CXCR4 as upregulated genes, and CCR5, XCL2, NCF1, CCR2, CX3CR1, PNP, CCR10, CCL3L1, CXCR3, and CCL3 as downregulated genes. CXCR3, CX3CR1, and CCR2 genes were selected for validation as they play an important role in PAE, regulating activation of microglia³¹.

Similarly, MAPK pathway was previously observed to be activated in mouse FASD model transcriptome analysis⁹. Our analysis identified DUSP4, FGF11, DUSP2 and DUSP8 as upregulated genes (Fig. 5b), while HSPB1, TNFRSK1A, JUN, PLA2G2D, CACNA1A, FASLG, DUSP1, HSPA6, IL1B, PDGFA, CACNA1E, HSPA1A, HSPA1B and FOS genes were downregulated. For RT-qPCR, we selected DUSP4 and FGF11 as the most significantly upregulated genes and FOS as a principal downstream effector of MAPK pathway and the most downregulated gene.

PPAR signaling controls the transcription of target genes related to immune response, lipid metabolism, oxidative stress, and inflammation³². RNAseq analysis identified APOA2 as an upregulated gene and NR1H3, SLC27A4, SLC27A1, OLR1, and APOA1 as downregulated genes (Fig. 5c), which are involved in lipid metabolism, oxidative stress, and inflammation regulation^{32,33}. OLR1 was selected for RT-qPCR validation as a direct transcriptional target of PPAR γ ³⁴ and has previously been described to promote microglial migration activation³⁵ and may improve cognition in FASD patients.

PAE activates the immune system through TLR and NLR receptors in CNS³⁶. Therefore, we focused on NOD-like receptor pathway in this study. Antigen processing and presentation, phagosome, endocytosis, and cytosolic DNA-sensing pathways were not selected for the research because blood sampling may potentially affect the high amount of RNA related to immunoglobulins and immune system cells. Our RNAseq analysis revealed an upregulation of TNFAIP3 gene, whereas CASP1, CASP5, MAPK14, MEFV, PSTPIP1, CARD6, CARD9, PYCARD, TRIP6, NLR4, and IL1B genes were downregulated (Fig. 5d). For RT-qPCR validation, TNFAIP3 and CASP5 were chosen as the most up- and downregulated genes, respectively, and are involved in NF- κ B and inflammasome^{37–39}.

Peroxisome signaling is implicated in fatty acid oxidation⁴⁰, oxidative stress, and ROS production⁴⁰, which causes neuronal apoptosis in FASD⁴¹. The results showed that the peroxisome pathway was mainly downregulated after EGCG treatment in FASD patients, with ABCD2 as an upregulated gene and ACOX1, PXMP4, PEX6, PRDX5, IDH1, HMGCL, ECH1, PEX12, PMVK as downregulated genes (Fig. 5e). ABCD2 and PMVK were selected for validation as the most up- and downregulated genes, respectively.

Pathways related to osteoclast differentiation, RNA transport, spliceosome, protein processing in endoplasmic reticulum, and amino sugar and nucleotide sugar metabolism were not selected for RNAseq validation due to their unclear impact on FASD neurodevelopmental pathogenesis.

After RT-qPCR, our results showed that gene expression in chemokine pathway of CCR2, CX3CR1, CXCR3 were significantly downregulated after 12 months of treatment (Fig. 6a). In MAPK pathway (Fig. 6b), statistical analysis showed that DUSP4 and FGF11 were upregulated and FOS gene was downregulated after treatment. In PPAR pathway (Fig. 6c), OLR1 was significantly downregulated after EGCG treatment, while the expression levels of CASP5 and TNFAIP3, related to the NOD-like receptor pathway, showed significant down- and upregulation, respectively (Fig. 6d). Finally, in the peroxisome pathway, ABCD2 showed a significant upregulation, whereas PMVK showed the opposite behavior (Fig. 6e). All these results confirmed the findings obtained by RNAseq analysis.

Safety outcome

The safety and tolerability of the product were good, with no clinically relevant biochemical alterations observed during the study period. No significant differences were detected in glucose levels ($p=0.417$), AST ($p=0.913$) or cholesterol ($p=0.715$) between baseline and twelve months. ALT showed a small increase that did not reach statistical significance ($p=0.068$). Triglycerides showed a significant decrease over time ($p=0.0036$), with a decrease of 36 points by the end of the study (Supplementary Figure S5).

Fig. 2. Neurocognitive assessment. Comparison of neuropsychological profiles of FASD at baseline, 6 and 12 months after EGCG treatment. (A) WISC-IV test. (B) CBCL 6–18 test. (C) NEPSY-II test. Affect Recognition (AR); Comprehension of Instructions (CI); Design Copying (DC); Full-Scale IQ (FSIQ); Initial Word Generation (IWG); List Memory & List Memory Delayed (LM&LMD); Memory for Faces (MF); Memory for Faces Delayed (MFD); Narrative Memory (NM); Perceptual Reasoning Index (PRI); Processing Speed Index (PSI); Semantic Word Generation (SWG); Theory of Mind (TM); Verbal Comprehension Index (VCI); Visuomotor Precision Combined (VPC); Visuomotor Precision Time (VPTS); Working Memory Index (WMI). Data are represented as mean ± SEM of each score. Black line shows distribution of FASD at baseline, gray line shows distribution after 6 months and red line shows distribution after 12 months of EGCG treatment. Blue box indicates borderline range (when applicable). For WISC: 70–79; for CBCL: 60–63; NEPSY-II does not define a borderline range — scores are classified as well below, below, average, above, or well above expected. Significance indicated for comparisons between FASD patients at baseline and after 12 months of treatment. ****, $p < 0.001$, ***, $p < 0.005$, **, $p < 0.01$, *, $p < 0.05$.

Fig. 3. Levels of oxidative stress biomarkers at baseline, 6 and 12 months after EGCG treatment. Serum concentrations of 8-isoprostane (A), malondialdehyde (B) and NADH+ (C) in FASD children were compared. Data are presented as mean \pm SEM. Comparisons across time points were performed using paired statistical tests (Wilcoxon signed-rank test). * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

Discussion

This study has evaluated the therapeutic potential of EGCG to improve cognitive and behavioral performance in FASD, showing significant improvements in cognitive and behavioral variables. Furthermore, EGCG induced significant changes in the transcriptomic profiles, modulating key pathways related to CNS function, oxidative stress, anti-inflammatory response, and immune system regulation.

Levels of MDA, 8-isoprostane, and LDH biomarkers after EGCG treatment demonstrated that this antioxidant significantly reduced oxidative stress in FASD, confirming previous observations in other pathologies^{42,43}. Moreover, molecular changes observed after EGCG treatment correspond to its documented health benefits, including anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidative properties⁴⁴ by suppressing NLRP3 inflammasome⁴⁵ and modulating the expression of MAPK⁴⁶, PPAR γ ⁴⁷ and NLR family⁴⁸.

Previous studies highlighted that EGCG could prevent embryonic damage caused by PAE, including growth restriction, neurodevelopmental maturation, and differentiation²⁵. Our study has demonstrated significant improvements in intellectual functioning area (WISC-IV) in FASD, including perceptual reasoning, understanding visual information, and non-verbal reasoning. Additionally, working memory, which involves memorization and manipulation of new information, improved in FASD after one year of treatment with EGCG. Executive functioning (NEPSY-II) improved significantly in the ability for face memory. These results are associated with motor plus visual-perceptual skills. Results obtained in problem behavior area (CBCL 6–18) showed a significant decrease in aggressive behavior, one of the main problems in FASD⁴⁹. Our findings are consistent with previous studies which observed improved memory and executive function after EGCG treatment in middle-aged and elderly subjects⁵⁰, DS²¹ and Alzheimer¹⁹. Similar results were observed in studies of choline supplementation in FASD cohorts. Wozniak et al. examined cognitive variables and demonstrated an increased capacity for long-delayed memory in FASD⁵¹. Consistent with our results, Nguyen et al. documented an alleviation in memory deficits and an improvement in executive function. However, in line with our findings, their investigations also did not reveal favorable results on measures of attention deficit⁵².

Our transcriptomic analysis provided valuable insights into molecular mechanisms underlying the therapeutic effects of EGCG in FASD. Previous transcriptomic studies in FASD performed in animal models discovered dysregulated pathways related to neurodevelopment, inflammation, and immune function pathways^{9,13,53}. Our study was conducted using blood samples from children with FASD, underscoring that human pediatric samples offer a direct connection to clinical practice, making our findings particularly relevant for translational research and potential therapeutic applications.

Enriched pathways were linked to pro-inflammatory response downregulation after EGCG treatment, as chemokine, MAPK, and PPAR pathways. Chemokines released by neurons, microglia, or astrocytes play a crucial role in CNS⁵⁴. According to RT-qPCR results, CXCR3, CX3CR1, and CCR2 expression levels were significantly downregulated after EGCG treatment. These molecules essential for immune cell activation, are associated with neurodegeneration and inflammation^{55–57}. Our results indicate that EGCG reduces pro-inflammatory chemokines, as previously confirmed^{58–60}.

EGCG inhibits MAPK activation by decreasing ROS⁶¹ and ERK activity⁶², also implicated in neuroinflammatory processes⁶³. Chemokines activate MAPK and PI3K pathways through CXCR3, CX3CR1, and CCR2^{64–67}. RT-qPCR showed upregulation of DUSP4 and FGF11 and downregulation of FOS after EGCG treatment. Neuronal DUSP4 overexpression is associated with a decrease in cytokines, chemokines, and IFN γ , reducing neuroinflammation⁶⁸. Although its function in humans is not fully understood, FGF11 mouse homolog is associated with CNS development⁶⁹ and might promote neural development in humans. Moreover, FOS, a downstream target of the MAPK cascade, activates AP-1, a modulator in inflammatory diseases⁷⁰. The specific roles of DUSP4, which negatively regulates the MAPK pathway⁷¹ and induces FOS reduction, confirm that MAPK downregulation could have a potential role in dampening inflammation after EGCG treatment in FASD.

Fig. 4. Transcriptomic analysis in FASD patients after EGCG treatment. (A) Volcano plot indicates effect size (Log₂FoldChange) and significance (Log₁₀pvalue) for each transcript comparing at baseline and after EGCG treatment. Red dots are up-regulated significant genes and blue dots are down-regulated significant genes. (B) Circular Diagram indicates 6635 differentially expressed genes in the transcriptomic analysis. (C) KEGG pathways were observed with significant genes comparing before and after EGCG treatment.

PPAR nuclear receptors regulate genes involved in immunity, lipid metabolism, oxidative stress, and inflammation³². Our findings indicate that PPAR signaling was downregulated after EGCG treatment. RT-qPCR confirmed OLR1 downregulation, a direct PPAR γ target³⁴. Studies revealed that OLR1 and CCL2 promote neuroinflammation through microglial activation, and their expression is reduced after anti-inflammatory treatment with OPC scFvD3-1³⁵. In the same line, our results indicated downregulation of OLR1 and CCR2 expression, confirming the anti-inflammatory effect of EGCG.

NLR signaling also plays role in inflammatory and immune-related pathways. Studies showed that alcohol stimulates astrocytes and microglia activity through the activation of TLR and NLR, resulting in activation of NF- κ B, MAPK signaling, and cytokines⁷². Our results showed TNFAIP3 upregulation and CASP5 downregulation. TNFAIP3 acts as a negative feedback regulator of NF- κ B, NLR, and apoptosis cascades⁷³. CASP5 is a caspase

Fig. 5. Heatmap of enriched pathways after treatment. Heatmap shows DEGs genes comparing at baseline and after EGCG treatment. Analysis was performed with FDR < 0.05, FoldChange (FC) > 1.8 and < 0.7. Downregulated genes are indicated in blue and upregulated in red.

involved in inflammation and apoptosis³⁹, and an NLR target³⁸. Our findings suggest that EGCG treatment may reduce inflammation and apoptosis through NLR signaling, inducing TNFAIP3 upregulation and observing CASP5 downregulation by reducing NF- κ B activation and pro-inflammatory cytokine release.

EGCG can regulate peroxisome-signaling, responsible for fatty acid oxidation and ROS metabolism⁴⁰. ABCD2, which was significantly upregulated, is involved in fatty acid metabolism and peroxisome biogenesis⁷⁴. Its downregulation is associated with proinflammatory cytokines⁷⁵ and oxidative stress⁷⁶. PMVK, significantly downregulated after EGCG treatment, is involved in the mevalonate pathway⁷⁷, which can induce inflammatory and immune responses⁷⁸. Therefore, EGCG increases ABCD2 and reduces PMVK expression, which may modulate oxidative stress and inflammatory response dysregulated in FASD.

Although canonical mitochondrial pathways (e.g., oxidative phosphorylation or TCA cycle) did not emerge as significantly enriched in our analysis, PPAR signaling and peroxisome-related pathways are tightly interconnected

Fig. 6. RT-qPCR validation of RNAseq results. Validation of 11 DEGs identified in FASD children before and after EGCG treatment. Relative expression levels of each gene were calculated using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method. Data are represented as mean \pm SEM. **** $p < 0.001$.

with mitochondrial function. PPAR activation regulates mitochondrial β -oxidation and biogenesis through PGC-1 α co-activation, shaping cellular energy metabolism and ROS homeostasis⁷⁹. Likewise, peroxisomes engage in extensive metabolic crosstalk with mitochondria, coordinating lipid catabolism and reactive oxygen species detoxification, and alterations in peroxisomal activity can directly impact mitochondrial performance⁸⁰. Therefore, the modulation of PPAR signaling and peroxisomal genes observed after EGCG treatment may reflect indirect regulatory effects on mitochondrial-associated metabolic processes.

Our study found that EGCG improved intellectual, executive, and behavioral outcomes in children with FASD. These results may be attributed to EGCG's regulation of genes and pathways that promote synaptic plasticity, memory, emotional processing, and limbic system, such as MAPK-pathway^{81,82}, which has also been implicated in aggressive behavior, social anxiety, and social defeat⁸³. Additionally, PPAR γ regulation promotes axonal growth and myelination, supporting cognitive function⁸⁴. EGCG peroxisome may interact with BDNF-TrkB in the adult brain⁸⁵, contributing to memory, synaptic plasticity, and neurogenesis⁸⁶. Additionally, DUSP4 family has been studied for their activity in neuronal differentiation⁸⁷, embryonic stem cell neurogenesis⁸⁸, axon development⁸⁹ and neuroprotection⁹⁰. FGF family plays crucial role in adult neural proliferation and regenerative processes⁹¹ and FGF11 plays a role in mouse limb development⁶⁹. Our findings also support that FontUp is safe and well tolerated, in line with the results of the PERSEUS study conducted in children aged 6 to 12 years with Down syndrome²⁰. While our study provides preliminary insights into the potential therapeutic effects of EGCG in FASD, further research is required to clarify the mechanisms through which EGCG may influence cognition and behavior in humans. In a FASD-like mouse model, our group showed that EGCG restored markers of neuronal maturation (NeuN, GFAP), enhanced synaptic plasticity signatures (BDNF, DYRK1A), and improved learning and memory performance in Rotarod, T-maze and Morris water maze tests⁹². All these results suggest that EGCG has the potential to modulate neuronal development and synaptic plasticity. However, additional mechanistic studies in humans are needed to substantiate this hypothesis.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates the therapeutic potential of EGCG to improve some cognitive and behavioral variables, including perceptual reasoning, memory, and to reduce aggressive behavior in FASD patients. Interestingly, EGCG did not differentially improve intelligence quotient, anxiety, or depression, which are domains particularly vulnerable in FASD patients. Transcriptomic analysis revealed changes in critical pathways related to anti-inflammatory responses, immune system, and antioxidant response. Our findings provide, for the first time, evidence of the ability of EGCG-based treatments to induce changes at the molecular level that translate into improved cognitive performance in this population, potentially improving the quality of life of patients and their families.

Limitations of the study

EGCG shows promise as a therapeutic candidate for improving cognition and behavior in FASD. However, some limitations should be considered. The age range of 5 to 16 years, and the lack of sex-based analysis, may introduce biases related to childhood and adolescent growth. However, our pre-post design allows individualized assessments by comparing each participant to their baseline, reducing biases associated with inter-individual variability. The sample size and the reduced number of participants retained at 12 months may limit the statistical power and the ability to detect modest treatment effects. People who dropped out of the trial may have caused an attrition bias, introducing a bias into the estimated effect. CBCL scales were assessed at baseline and after 12 months to minimize participant burden and ensure higher compliance, limiting the impact that 6-month assessments might have on increasing participant dropout due to fatigue, despite the potential loss of information on behavioral change midway through the study. Another limitation is the open-label design, which may have introduced expectation bias in parent-reported outcomes such as the CBCL. Nonetheless, the consistency of improvements across objective cognitive measures (WISC-IV, NEPSY-II) and molecular biomarkers supports the robustness of our findings. Future randomized, double-blind studies are warranted to confirm these results. Although oxidative stress biomarkers were measured at all time points, the number of paired samples available after 12 months of treatment was limited. This can reduce the statistical power and limit the generalisability of the findings. Furthermore, the sample size of 8 patients in pre- and post-transcriptomic analyses could prevent the detection of critical pathways altered in FASD patients due to slight effects in gene expression after EGCG treatment, which could be significant with a larger sample size.

Future research should consider age-stratified analyses to better understand the differential effects of EGCG across FASD. It would be valuable to investigate unexplored facets of EGCG's effects, such as osteoclast differentiation pathway, and unexplored genes such as IL-1B downregulation present in NLR signaling, by techniques such as Luminex or ELISA. Additionally, because mitochondrial pathways did not reach significance in this dataset, future studies with larger cohorts should include targeted analyses of mitochondrial function to determine whether EGCG may exert effects not detectable in this pilot sample.

Methods

Experimental model and participants

Pre-post, open-label, non-randomized pilot study assessed the efficacy of FontUp, a nutritional supplement containing 94% EGCG in improving cognitive performance for children with FASD. FontUp offers longer half-life, greater stability, and lower inter-individual variability than EGCG alone⁹³.

The study included 40 patients adopted from EEC, diagnosed with FASD. Participants received EGCG for one year, with blood collection at baseline, 6 and 12 months of treatment for oxidative stress, and transcriptomic analysis. The use of placebo was not permitted in this study because the Ethical Committee deemed it unethical to withhold effective treatment from children, especially for serious conditions. Pediatric trials have stricter regulations on placebos than adult trials, and the Declaration of Helsinki requires that all children receive the best-proven treatment^{94,95}. Since prior evidence supported the trial therapy's efficacy, using a placebo would have been unethical^{20,21}.

The recruited pediatric cohorts belonged to previous projects (PI13/01135;OG085818; PI16/00566; PI19/01853). The study was conducted at Hospital del Mar Medical Research Institute and the Hospital Clinic of Barcelona. Enrollment took place from February 2016 to July 2018.

Clinical trial registration

This study was conducted as part of a registered clinical trial entitled "Epigallocatechin Gallate (EGCG) to Improve Cognitive Performance in Foetal Alcohol Syndrome (FAS) Children (Neuro-SAF)", registered at ClinicalTrials.gov (Identifier: NCT02558933).

The trial was registered on 22 September 2015, prior to the enrolment of participants, and is publicly accessible through the World Health Organization International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO ICTRP).

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria included adopted subjects (5 to 16 years) from EEC, diagnosed with FASD, residing in Spain. Participants' guardians consent to supplement administration and to attend all visits. Exclusion criteria included (i) severe neurological disorders or psychiatric conditions, (ii) use of cognitive stimulatory treatment, and (iii) taking antioxidants, vitamins, or green tea.

Intervention

Patients diagnosed with FASD received 9 mg/kg/day of EGCG through FontUp, a cocoa-flavored nutritional powder provided by the study investigator, a pediatrician specialized in FASD. The supplement was administered at home by caregivers, dissolved in 200 mL of semi-skimmed milk according to written instructions⁹³. The 9 mg/kg/day dose is grounded in prior pediatric research^{20,21}, and maximum daily limit of 400 mg. FontUp was purchased from Grand Fontaine Laboratories (Barcelona, Spain). Adherence was monitored through caregiver reports and weight assessments were conducted at baseline, 6, and 12 months to adjust dosage. No major deviations from the administration protocol were observed.

FontUp is composed of fats, carbohydrates, proteins, vitamins, minerals, and 94% EGCG (Supplementary Table S6), with these supplementary components specifically designed to improve EGCG's stability and bioavailability⁹³.

Adverse events were assessed at 6- and 12-month visits through structured interviews with caregivers, asking about any changes in behavior, health, or well-being. No severe adverse events or treatment discontinuations

were reported. Previous clinical studies have reported that daily doses of 9 mg/kg of EGCG are well-tolerated, without adverse effects on liver or cardiac function⁹⁶.

Neurocognitive assessment

Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children (WISC-IV) Fourth Edition⁹⁷ was performed to evaluate cognitive domain. Scores ≤ 70 in three or more domains indicated cognitive delay. Administered at baseline for all participants and 6 and 12 months for FASD. Test-retest was defined in 35 days, and literature declares a 6-months-retest appropriate⁹⁸. Additionally, studies showed that intelligence-scores in FASD remain stable over time^{99,100}, making it unlikely that the improvements observed result from natural cognitive development.

Parental report of behavioral concerns was obtained using the Child Behavior Checklist (CBCL)¹⁰¹. Scores ≥ 70 were considered significant. Administered at baseline for all participants and 12 months for FASD.

Other neurocognitive measures were obtained from NEPSY-II¹⁰², covering five different domains: language, memory and learning, social perception, visuospatial processing, and sensorimotor. Delays were defined as scores ≤ 5 . Administered to FASD participants at baseline, 6, and 12 months. Test-retest is 21 days, which demonstrates adequate reliability for retesting¹⁰³. Furthermore, studies demonstrated that intelligence-scores remained stable after 8 years in FASD⁹⁹.

FASD diagnosis

Participants were diagnosed according to 1996 Institute of Medicine (IOM) criteria^{104,105}, based on 5 characteristics: (1) confirmed PAE; (2) minor facial abnormalities (thin upper-lip, smooth-philtrum, and short palpebral fissures); (3) growth retardation (height or weight \leq 10th percentile); (4) brain growth deficiency; and (5) behavioral or cognitive impairments. FAS diagnosis criteria 2, 3, 4, 5 were required. Partial FAS criteria 1, 2, and at least one of criteria 5 or 2, 5, and 3 or 4 were required. Alcohol-related birth defects (ARBD) require the presence of 1 criterion plus 1 structural defect (heart, face, skeleton, kidney, eye, ear, or hands). Alcohol-related neurodevelopmental disorder (ARND) diagnosis required 1 and 5 criteria.

Blood collection and processing

5 mL of blood was collected in BD Vacutainer SST II Advance (BD Biosciences;367955) at baseline, 6, and 12 months. Blood samples were centrifuged at 1750 g for 10 min at 4 °C immediately after collection to obtain serum. Two 5 mL tubes of blood were collected in BD Vacutainer K3E 15% Aprotinin 250KIU (SGSH; BD361017). Peripheral blood mononuclear cells were isolated by centrifugation in Blood Collection tube BD Vacutainer, BD CPT (Avantor, BDAM362781). RNA was isolated using QIAshredder (Qiagen,79654) and RNAsy Mini-Kit (Qiagen, 74104) protocols. RNA quantification was performed by Nanodrop One (Thermo Fisher Scientific). RNA included had a 260/280 ratio and a 260/260 ratio > 1.8 . RNA integrity (RIN > 8) was verified by Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer before transcriptomic analysis.

Oxidative stress biomarkers

ROS production was evaluated by measuring lipid-peroxidation metabolites as malondialdehyde (MDA), 8-isoprostane, and enzymatic activity of lactate-dehydrogenase (LDH) in serum at baseline, 6 and 12 months of treatment. MDA was analyzed using lipid peroxidation (MDA) Assay kit (Abcam; ab118970). 8-Isoprostane was evaluated by ELISA (Abcam; ab175819). LDH was measured by Lactate Dehydrogenase Activity Assay Kit (Sigma Aldrich; MAK066). All samples were analyzed in duplicate, and none exceeded the detection or quantification limits.

RNA sequencing (RNAseq)

RNA was analyzed at Microomics Systems S.L. using an Illumina TruSeq Stranded mRNA, yielding 2×125 bp sequences. Quality-control was evaluated using FastQC. Pre-processing with Trimmomatic, alignment to GRCh38 with STAR, and alignment quality-control with FastQC and MultiQC. Reads were counted with featureCounts. Differential expression was analyzed in R (v4.3.1) using DESeq2 with a paired design to compare baseline and 12-month samples. P-values were adjusted using the Benjamini-Hochberg FDR, and genes with FDR < 0.05 were considered significant. Data normalization and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was achieved with DESeq2 package. Gene annotation was obtained using org.Hs.eg.db package. Enrichment pathway analysis was performed using gage packages.

RT-qPCR validation

Reverse transcription was performed using Applied Biosystems High Capacity cDNA Reverse Transcription kit (Fisher Scientific;10400745). RT-qPCR was performed using PerfeCTa SYBR Green FastMix (Quantabio;95074-012) in QuantStudioTM 7 (Thermo Fisher Scientific; 4485701). GAPDH served as reference gene. Primers provided by Sigma Aldrich are listed in Supplementary Table S7. The $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ method assessed relative abundance.

Study outcomes

The primary outcomes were improvements in cognitive, executive, and behavioral function, assessed using the WISC-IV, NEPSY-II, and CBCL 6–18. Secondary outcomes included oxidative stress biomarkers (MDA, 8-isoprostane, LDH) and molecular changes in gene expression profiles, assessed through RNAseq and validated by RT-qPCR.

Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed using SPSS (IBM), GraphPad, and R project. Descriptive statistics included mean and standard deviation (SD). Given the sample size and the non-normal distribution of the data, non-parametric tests were selected. For oxidative stress biomarkers, we performed a paired Wilcoxon signed-rank test comparing baseline vs. 6 months and baseline vs. 12 months. For neurocognitive outcomes, we conducted pre-specified paired comparisons of baseline vs. 6 months and baseline vs. 12 months using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. To control for multiple testing across these pairwise comparisons, p-values were adjusted using the Holm–Bonferroni procedure (two-sided $\alpha=0.05$). Sensitivity analyses (G*Power) indicated that with $n=33$ pairs the study had 80% power (two-tailed $\alpha=0.05$) to detect a minimum effect size of $d_z=0.52$, and with $n=24$ pairs the minimum detectable effect was $d_z=0.61$. Therefore, the study was adequately powered to detect medium-to-large effects, but smaller effects may not have been captured. Post hoc power analysis indicated that, for the neurocognitive outcomes analyzed, the study had sufficient power to detect medium-to-large effects, with $n=33$ yielding a power of 0.79 (noncentrality parameter=2.86, $df=30.5$, critical $t=2.04$) and $n=24$ yielding a power of 0.79 (noncentrality parameter=2.92, $df=21.9$, critical $t=2.07$). These results suggest that the significant improvements observed are robust, although smaller effects may not have been detectable due to the limited sample size. Statistical significance was set at $p<0.05$. All participants with available data at each time point were included in the analyses. Missing data resulted from non-compliance or inadequate RNA quality. These cases were excluded from the corresponding analyses without data imputation.

Data availability

RNAseq data is available in the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) repository under accession number GSE307141. Anonymized neurocognitive and oxidative stress datasets supporting the findings of this study are publicly available in the Zenodo repository, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18078285>.

Received: 16 September 2025; Accepted: 30 December 2025

Published online: 02 January 2026

References

- Clave, S., Joya, X., Salat-Batlle, J. & Garcia-Algar, O. Vall, O. Ethanol cytotoxic effect on trophoblast cells. *Toxicol. Lett.* **225**, 216–221 (2014).
- Lange, S., Rovet, J., Rehm, J. & Popova, S. Neurodevelopmental profile of fetal alcohol spectrum disorder: A systematic review. *BMC Psychol.* **5**, 22 (2017).
- Lange, S. et al. Global prevalence of fetal alcohol spectrum disorder among children and youth: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *JAMA Pediatr.* **171**, 948–956 (2017).
- Bubnov, A. A. *Morpho-functional Diagnosis of the Consequences of Prenatal Alcohol Exposure during Pregnancy in Early Childhood* [(МОРФО-ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ДИАГНОСТИКА ПОСЛЕДСТВИЙ ВНУТРИУТРОБНОГО АЛКОГОЛЬНОГО ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ У ДЕТЕЙ РАННЕГО ВОЗРАСТА), 2010].
- Legon'kova, S. V. Clinical and functional characteristics of fetal alcohol syndrome in early childhood [Клинико-функциональная характеристика фетального алкогольного синдрома у детей раннего возраста]. Preprint at: <https://dissercat.com/content/kl-iniko-funktsionalnaya-kharakteristika-fetalnogo-alkogolnogo-sindroma-u-detei-rannego-vozra> (2011).
- Colom, J. et al. Prevalence of fetal alcohol spectrum disorders (FASD) among children adopted from Eastern European countries: Russia and Ukraine. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health.* **18**, 1–12 (2021).
- Brocardo, P. S., Gil-Mohapel, J. & Christie, B. R. The role of oxidative stress in fetal alcohol spectrum disorders. *Brain Res. Rev.* **67**, 209–225 (2011).
- Wilhelm, C. J. & Guizzetti, M. Fetal alcohol spectrum disorders: an overview from the glia perspective. *Front Integr. Neurosci.* **9**, 65 (2015).
- Alberry, B. L. J., Castellani, C. A. & Singh, S. M. Hippocampal transcriptome analysis following maternal separation implicates altered RNA processing in a mouse model of fetal alcohol spectrum disorder. *J Neurodev Disord.* **12**, 15 (2020).
- Valenti, D. & Vacca, R. A. Brain mitochondrial bioenergetics in genetic neurodevelopmental disorders: focus on down, Rett and fragile X syndromes. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **2023**, 24, 12488 (2023).
- Basel, A. et al. Parental alcohol exposures associate with lasting mitochondrial dysfunction and accelerated aging in a mouse model. *Aging Dis.* **16**, 2408–2425 (2025).
- Jamali, Z., Salimi, A., Garmabi, B., Khezri, S. & Khaksari, M. Hesperidin protects alcohol-induced mitochondrial abnormalities via the Inhibition of oxidative stress and MPT pore opening in newborn male rats as a fetal alcohol syndrome model. *J Stud Alcohol Drugs.* **85**, 361–370. <https://doi.org/10.15288/jsad.23-00243> (2024).
- Lunde-Young, R. et al. Hippocampal transcriptome reveals novel targets of FASD pathogenesis. *Brain Behav.* **9**, e01334 (2019).
- Salem, N. A., Mahnke, A. H., Konganti, K., Hillhouse, A. E. & Miranda, R. C. Cell-type and fetal-sex-specific targets of prenatal alcohol exposure in developing mouse cerebral cortex. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jisci.2021.102439> (2021).
- Vieiros, M. et al. Analysis of alcohol-metabolizing enzymes genetic variants and RAR/RXR expression in patients diagnosed with fetal alcohol syndrome: a case-control study. *BMC Genomics* **2024**, 25:1 25, 1–16 (2024).
- Ramos-Triguero, A. et al. Machine learning algorithms to the early diagnosis of fetal alcohol spectrum disorders. *Front. Neurosci.* **18**, 1400933 (2024).
- Peadar, E., Rhys-Jones, B., Bower, C. & Elliott, E. J. Systematic review of interventions for children with fetal alcohol spectrum disorders. *BMC Pediatr.* **9**, 35 (2009).
- Premji, S., Benzies, K., Serrett, K. & Hayden, K. A. Research-based interventions for children and youth with a fetal alcohol spectrum disorder: revealing the gap. *Child. Care Health Dev.* **33**, 389–397 (2007).
- Casella, M., Bimonte, S., Muzio, M. R., Schiavone, V. & Cuomo, A. The efficacy of Epigallocatechin-3-gallate (green tea) in the treatment of alzheimer's disease: an overview of pre-clinical studies and translational perspectives in clinical practice. *Infect Agent Cancer.* **12**, 36 (2017).
- Cieuta-Walti, C. et al. Safety and preliminary efficacy on cognitive performance and adaptive functionality of Epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG) in children with down syndrome. A randomized phase Ib clinical trial (PERSEUS study). *Genet. Med.* **24**, 2004–2013 (2022).
- de la Torre, R. Safety and efficacy of cognitive training plus epigallocatechin-3-gallate in young adults with down's syndrome (TESDAD): a double-blind, randomised, placebo-controlled, phase 2 trial. *Lancet Neurol.* **15**, 801–810 (2016).
- Solzak, J. P., Liang, Y., Zhou, F. C. & Roper, R. J. Commonality in down and fetal alcohol syndromes. *Birth Defects Res. Clin. Mol. Teratol.* **97**, 187 (2013).

23. Scala, I. et al. Epigallocatechin-3-gallate plus omega-3 restores the mitochondrial complex i and f0f1-atp synthase activities in Pbmcs of young children with down syndrome: a pilot study of safety and efficacy. *Antioxid.* **2021**, **10**, Page 469 (10), 469 (2021).
24. Saffari, Y. & Sadrzadeh, S. M. H. Green tea metabolite EGCG protects membranes against oxidative damage in vitro. *Life Sci.* **74**, 1513–1518 (2004).
25. Almeida-Toledano, L. et al. Epigallocatechin gallate ameliorates the effects of prenatal alcohol exposure in a fetal alcohol spectrum disorder-like mouse model. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **22**, 1–24 (2021).
26. Ayala, A., Muñoz, M. F. & Argüelles, S. Lipid peroxidation: production, metabolism, and signaling mechanisms of malondialdehyde and 4-hydroxy-2-nonenal. *Oxid Med Cell Longev* (2014). (2014).
27. Rahma, A. & Kusharto, C. M. IOP Conference series: earth and environmental science single and mixture administration of white tea (*Camellia sinensis*) and moringa (*Moringa oleifera*) as antihyperglycemia in diabetic male rats (Sprague-dawley) induced by streptozotocin. *IOP Conf. Series: Earth and Environmental Science* **196**, 12042 (2018).
28. Kanehisa, M. & Goto, S. K. E. G. G. Kyoto encyclopedia of genes and genomes. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **28**, 27–30 (2000).
29. Kanehisa, M., Furumichi, M., Sato, Y., Matsuura, Y. & Ishiguro-Watanabe, M. KEGG: biological systems database as a model of the real world. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **53**, D672–D677 (2025).
30. Kanehisa, M. Toward Understanding the origin and evolution of cellular organisms. *Protein Sci.* **28**, 1947–1951 (2019).
31. Kane, C. J. M. & Drew, P. D. Inflammatory responses to alcohol in the CNS: nuclear receptors as potential therapeutics for alcohol-induced neuropathologies. *J. Leukoc. Biol.* **100**, 951–959 (2016).
32. Bougarne, N. et al. Molecular actions of PPARα in lipid metabolism and inflammation. *Endocr. Rev.* **39**, 760–802 (2018).
33. Scazzocchio, B. et al. Oxidized LDL impair adipocyte response to insulin by activating serine/threonine kinases. *J. Lipid Res.* **50**, 832 (2009).
34. Chui, P. C., Guan, H. P., Lehrke, M. & Lazar, M. A. PPARγ regulates adipocyte cholesterol metabolism via oxidized LDL receptor 1. *J. Clin. Invest.* **115**, 2244 (2005).
35. Minamiyama, S. et al. Efficacy of oligodendrocyte precursor cells as delivery vehicles for single-chain variable fragment to misfolded SOD1 in ALS rat model. *Mol. Ther. Methods Clin. Dev.* **28**, 312–329 (2023).
36. Noor, S. & Milligan, E. D. Lifelong impacts of moderate prenatal alcohol exposure on neuroimmune function. *Front. Immunol.* **9**, 1107 (2018).
37. Saxena, M. & Yeretssian, G. NOD-like receptors: master regulators of inflammation and cancer. *Front. Immunol.* **5**, 98103 (2014).
38. Tervaniemi, M. H. et al. NOD-like receptor signaling and inflammasome-related pathways are highlighted in psoriatic epidermis. *Scientific Reports* **2016** *6*:1 6, 1–12 (2016).
39. Bian, Z. M. et al. Expression and functional roles of caspase-5 in inflammatory responses of human retinal pigment epithelial cells. *Invest. Ophthalmol. Vis. Sci.* **52**, 8646 (2011).
40. Tripathi, D. N. & Walker, C. L. The peroxisome as a cell signaling organelle. *Curr. Opin. Cell. Biol.* **39**, 109 (2016).
41. Hernández, J. A., López-Sánchez, R. C. & Rendón-Ramírez, A. Lipids and oxidative stress associated with ethanol-induced neurological damage. *Oxid Med Cell Longev* (2016). (2016).
42. Liang, Y. et al. (-)-Epigallocatechin-3-gallate reduces cigarette smoke-induced airway neutrophilic inflammation and mucin hypersecretion in rats. *Front Pharmacol.* **8**, 618 (2017).
43. Sebastiani, G. et al. Therapeutic effects of catechins in less common neurological and neurodegenerative disorders. *Nutrients* **13**, 2232 (2021).
44. Andreu-Fernández, V. et al. Effect of postnatal epigallocatechin-gallate treatment on cardiac function in mice prenatally exposed to alcohol. *Antioxid.* **2023**, **12**, 1067 (2023).
45. Luo, Z. L., Sun, H. Y., Wu, X. B., Cheng, L. & Ren, J. D. Epigallocatechin-3-gallate attenuates acute pancreatitis induced lung injury by targeting mitochondrial reactive oxygen species triggered NLRP3 inflammasome activation. *Food Funct.* **12**, 5658–5667 (2021).
46. Shih, L. J., Chen, T. F., Lin, C. K., Liu, H. S. & Kao, Y. H. Green tea (-)-epigallocatechin gallate inhibits the growth of human villous trophoblasts via the ERK, p38, AMP-activated protein kinase, and protein kinase B pathways. *Am. J. Physiol. Cell. Physiol.* **311**, C308–C321 (2016).
47. Lee, K. Transactivation of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha by green tea extracts. *J. Vet. Sci.* **5**, 325–330 (2004).
48. Liu, C., Hao, K., Liu, Z., Liu, Z. & Guo, N. Epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG) attenuates Staphylococcal alpha-hemolysin (Hla)-induced NLRP3 inflammasome activation via ROS-MAPK pathways and EGCG-Hla interactions. *Int. Immunopharmacol.* **100**, 108170 (2021).
49. Joseph, J. J., Mela, M. & Pei, J. Aggressive behaviour and violence in children and adolescents with FASD: A synthesizing review. *Clin. Psychol. Rev.* **94**, 102155 (2022).
50. Zhang, R. et al. Green tea improves cognitive function through reducing AD-pathology and improving anti-oxidative stress capacity in Chinese middle-aged and elderly people. *Front. Aging Neurosci.* **14**, 919766 (2022).
51. Wozniak, J. R. et al. Choline supplementation in children with fetal alcohol spectrum disorders: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* **102**, 1113–1125 (2015).
52. Nguyen, T. T., Risbud, R. D., Mattson, S. N., Chambers, C. D. & Thomas, J. D. Randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled clinical trial of choline supplementation in school-aged children with fetal alcohol spectrum disorders. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* **104**, 1683–1692 (2016).
53. Lussier, A. A. et al. Prenatal alcohol exposure alters steady-state and activated gene expression in the adult rat brain. *Alcohol Clin. Exp. Res.* **39**, 251 (2015).
54. Wojcieszak, J., Kuczyńska, K. & Zawilska, J. B. Role of chemokines in the development and progression of Alzheimer's Disease. *Journal of Molecular Neuroscience* **2022** *72*:9 72, 1929–1951 (2022).
55. Heng, A. H. S., Han, C. W., Abbott, C., McColl, S. R. & Comerford, I. Chemokine-driven migration of pro-inflammatory CD4 + T cells in CNS autoimmune disease. *Front. Immunol.* **13**, 817473 (2022).
56. Chang, G. Q., Karatayev, O. & Leibowitz, S. F. Prenatal exposure to ethanol stimulates hypothalamic CCR2 chemokine receptor system: possible relation to increased density of orexigenic peptide neurons and ethanol drinking in adolescent offspring. *Neuroscience* **310**, 163–175 (2015).
57. Roberson, R., Kuddo, T., Benassou, I., Abebe, D. & Spong, C. Neuroprotective fractalkine in fetal alcohol syndrome. *Am. J. Obstet. Gynecol.* **204**, 400e1 (2011).
58. Liu, Q. et al. EGCG attenuates pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines production in LPS-stimulated L02 hepatocyte. *Acta Biochim. Biophys. Sin (Shanghai)*. **46**, 31–39 (2014).
59. Marotte, H., Ruth, J. H., Campbell, P. L., Koch, A. E. & Ahmed, S. Green tea extract inhibits chemokine production, but up-regulates chemokine receptor expression, in rheumatoid arthritis synovial fibroblasts and rat adjuvant-induced arthritis. *Rheumatol. (Oxford)*. **49**, 467 (2010).
60. Payne, A., Taka, E., Adinew, G. M. & Soliman, K. F. A. Molecular mechanisms of the anti-inflammatory effects of Epigallocatechin 3-Gallate (EGCG) in LPS-activated BV-2 microglia cells. *Brain Sci.* **2023**, **13**, 632 (2023).
61. Xu, D. et al. EGCG alleviates oxidative stress and inhibits aflatoxin B1 biosynthesis via MAPK signaling pathway. *Toxins* **2021**, **13**, 693 (2021).
62. Pan, X., Zhao, B., Song, Z., Han, S. & Wang, M. Estrogen receptor-α36 is involved in epigallocatechin-3-gallate induced growth inhibition of ER-negative breast cancer stem/progenitor cells. *J. Pharmacol. Sci.* **130**, 85–93 (2016).

63. Chen, M. J. et al. Microglial ERK signaling is a critical regulator of pro-inflammatory immune responses in alzheimer's disease. *BioRxiv* **798215** <https://doi.org/10.1101/798215> (2019).
64. Vilcek, J. *The Cytokines: an Overview. The Cytokine Handbook - Volume II* (Academic, 2003).
65. Zhuang, Z. Y. et al. Role of the CX3CR1/p38 MAPK pathway in spinal microglia for the development of neuropathic pain following nerve injury-induced cleavage of fractalkine. *Brain Behav. Immun.* **21**, 642–651 (2007).
66. Shahabuddin, S. et al. CXCR3 chemokine receptor-induced chemotaxis in human airway epithelial cells: role of p38 MAPK and PI3K signaling pathways. *Am J. Physiol. Cell. Physiol.* **291**, C34–C39 (2006).
67. Zhang, K. & Luo, J. Role of MCP-1 and CCR2 in alcohol neurotoxicity. *Pharmacol. Res.* **139**, 360 (2019).
68. Pan, A. L. et al. Dual-Specificity Protein Phosphatase 4 (DUSP4) Overexpression Improves Learning Behavior Selectively in Female 5xFAD Mice, and Reduces β -Amyloid Load in Males and Females. *Cells* **11**, (2022).
69. Tejedor, G. et al. Whole embryo culture, transcriptomics and RNA interference identify TBX1 and FGF11 as novel regulators of limb development in the mouse. *Sci Rep.* **10**, 3597 (2020).
70. Zenz, R. et al. Activator protein 1 (Fos/Jun) functions in inflammatory bone and skin disease. *Arthritis Res. Ther.* **10**, 1–10 (2008).
71. Balko, J. M. et al. Activation of MAPK pathways due to DUSP4 loss promotes cancer stem cell-like phenotypes in basal-like breast cancer. *Cancer Res.* **73**, 6346–6358 (2013).
72. Ramos, A., Joshi, R. S. & Szabo, G. Innate immune activation: parallels in alcohol use disorder and alzheimer's disease. *Front Mol. Neurosci.* **15**, 910298 (2022).
73. Vereecke, L., Beyaert, R. & Van Loo, G. Genetic relationships between A20/TNFAIP3, chronic inflammation and autoimmune disease. *Biochem. Soc. Trans.* **39**, 1086–1091 (2011).
74. Fourcade, S. et al. A key role for the peroxisomal ABCD2 transporter in fatty acid homeostasis. *Am J. Physiol. Endocrinol. Metab.* **296**, E211–21 (2009).
75. Singh, J., Khan, M. & Singh, I. Silencing of Abcd1 and Abcd2 genes sensitizes astrocytes for inflammation: implication for X-adrenoleukodystrophy. *J. Lipid Res.* **50**, 135–147 (2009).
76. Lu, J. F. et al. The role of peroxisomal ABC transporters in the mouse adrenal gland: the loss of Abcd2 (ALDR), not Abcd1 (ALD), causes oxidative damage. *Lab. Invest.* **87**, 261–272 (2007).
77. Yildiz, Ç. et al. A possibly new autoinflammatory disease due to compound heterozygous phosphomevalonate kinase gene mutation. *Joint Bone Spine.* **90**, 105490 (2023).
78. Pisanti, S. et al. Prenylation defects and oxidative stress trigger the main consequences of neuroinflammation linked to mevalonate pathway deregulation. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2022**, **19**, 9061 (2022).
79. Abu Shelbayeh, O., Arroum, T., Morris, S. & Busch, K. B. PGC-1 α is a master regulator of mitochondrial lifecycle and ROS stress response. *Antioxidants* **12**, 1075 (2023).
80. Demarquoy, J., Borgne, F. & Le Crosstalk between mitochondria and peroxisomes. *World J. Biol. Chem.* **6**, 301 (2015).
81. Schafe, G. E. et al. Activation of ERK/MAP kinase in the amygdala is required for memory consolidation of Pavlovian fear conditioning. *J. Neurosci.* **20**, 8177–8187 (2000).
82. Albert-Gascó, H., Ros-Bernal, F., Castillo-Gómez, E. & Olucha-Bordonau, F. E. MAP/ERK signaling in developing cognitive and emotional function and its effect on pathological and neurodegenerative processes. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **21**, 1–29 (2020).
83. Trainor, B. C., Crean, K. K., Fry, W. H. D. & Sweeney, C. Activation of extracellular signal-regulated kinases in social behavior circuits during resident-intruder aggression tests. *Neuroscience* **165**, 325 (2010).
84. Drew, P. D. & Kane, C. J. M. Peroxisome Proliferator-Activated Receptor- γ agonists: potential therapeutics for neuropathology associated with fetal alcohol spectrum disorders. *J. Clin. Cell. Immunol.* **7**, 469 (2016).
85. Abe, Y. et al. Peroxisome biogenesis deficiency attenuates the BDNF-TrkB pathway-mediated development of the cerebellum. *Life Sci. Alliance.* **1**, e201800062 (2018).
86. Park, H. & Poo, M. M. Neurotrophin regulation of neural circuit development and function. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience* **2013**, **14**:1 14, 7–23 (2012).
87. An, N. et al. Dual-specificity phosphatases in mental and neurological disorders. *Prog Neurobiol.* **198**, 101906 (2021).
88. Kim, S. Y. et al. DUSP4 regulates neuronal differentiation and calcium homeostasis by modulating ERK1/2 phosphorylation. *Stem Cells Dev.* **24**, 686 (2015).
89. Finelli, M. J., Murphy, K. J., Chen, L. & Zou, H. Differential phosphorylation of smad1 integrates BMP and neurotrophin pathways through Erk/Dusp in axon development. *Cell. Rep.* **3**, 1592 (2013).
90. Kyosseva, S. V. et al. Mitogen-activated protein kinases in schizophrenia. *Biol. Psychiatry.* **46**, 689–696 (1999).
91. Goldshmit, Y. et al. Different Fgfs have distinct roles in regulating neurogenesis after spinal cord injury in zebrafish. *Neural Dev.* **13**, 1–14 (2018).
92. Vieiros, M. et al. Effects of maternal drinking patterns and epigallocatechin-3-gallate treatment on behavioural and molecular outcomes in a mouse model of fetal alcohol spectrum disorders. *Biomed. Pharmacother.* **187**, 118138 (2025).
93. Fernández, V. A. et al. Bioavailability of Epigallocatechin gallate administered with different nutritional strategies in healthy volunteers. *Antioxidants* **9**, 440 (2020).
94. WMA Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects – WMA – the world medical association. <https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-declaration-of-helsinki-ethical-principles-for-medical-research-involving-human-subjects/>
95. Smyth, R. L. & Weindling, M. Research in Children: Ethical and Scientific Aspects. *The Lancet.* **354** Suppl 2:III21-4 (1999).
96. Gu, Y. et al. Molecular rescue of Dyrk1A overexpression alterations in mice with Fontup dietary supplement: role of green tea catechins. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **21**, 1404 (2020).
97. Kaufman, A. S., Flanagan, D. P., Alfonso, V. C. & Mascolo, J. T. Test review: Wechsler intelligence scale for Children, fourth edition (WISC-IV). *J. Psychoeduc Assess.* **24**, 278–295 (2006).
98. Ambreen, S. & Ajmal, M. Wechsler intelligence scale for children-fourth edition (wisc-iv): adaptation, translation, and standardization in pakistan. (2014).
99. Streissguth, A. P., Randels, S. P. & Smith, D. F. A test-retest study of intelligence in patients with fetal alcohol syndrome: implications for care. *J. Am. Acad. Child. Adolesc. Psychiatry.* **30**, 584–587 (1991).
100. Streissguth, A. P., Herman, C. S. & Smith, D. W. Stability of intelligence in the fetal alcohol syndrome: a preliminary report. *Alcohol Clin. Exp. Res.* **2**, 165–170 (1978).
101. Achenbach, T. M. Manual for the child: Behavior checklist and revised child behavior profile. *Encyclopedia of psychology*, Vol. 2. 2008–2009 (2004).
102. Davis, J. L. & Matthews, R. N. Nepsy-II review. *J. Psychoeduc Assess.* **28**, 175–182 (2010).
103. Sevadjan, C. & Denton, M. A. I confirmatory factor analysis of the nepsy: a developmental neuropsychological assessment, second edition in a mixed clinical sample of children. (2014).
104. Hoyme, H. E. et al. Updated clinical guidelines for diagnosing fetal alcohol spectrum disorders. *Pediatrics* **138**, e20154256 (2016).
105. Bastons-Compta, A., Astals, M., Andreu-Fernandez, V. & Navarro-Tapia, E. & Garcia-Algar, O. Postnatal nutritional treatment of neurocognitive deficits in fetal alcohol spectrum disorder. *Biochem Cell Biol.* **96**, 213–221. <https://doi.org/10.1139/bcb-2017-0085> (2017).

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge Visual TEAF, who contributed to patient recruitment and made this research possible.

Author contributions

A.R.-T. contributed to conceptualization, software, formal analysis, investigation, data curation, methodology, and wrote the original draft of the manuscript. E.N.-T. contributed to conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, and writing (original draft and review & editing). M.A.V. contributed to investigation, methodology, and writing (review & editing). M.V. contributed to investigation, methodology, and writing (review & editing). A.B.-C. contributed to investigation and methodology. L.M. contributed to investigation, methodology, and funding acquisition. V.A.-F. contributed to conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, supervision, project administration, and writing (original draft and review & editing). O.G.-A. contributed to conceptualization, investigation, methodology, supervision, funding acquisition, and writing (review & editing).

Funding

This research was funded by Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII) and co-funded by the European Union (projects RD24/0013/0019 - Spanish network in maternal, neonatal, child and developmental health research RICORS-SAMID, PI19/01853, PI23/01220, PI21/01415) and European Union - NextGenerationEU/Mecanismo para la Recuperación y la Resiliencia (MRR)/Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia (PRTR)(project RD21/0012/0017), Fundación Mutua Madrileña (ref. AP183662023), and with support of the Departament de Recerca i Universitats de la Generalitat de Catalunya al Grup de Recerca Infància i Entorn (GRIE) (2021 SGR 01290). The funders had no role in study design, data collection and analysis, decision to publish, or preparation of the manuscript.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics declarations

The study protocol was approved by the Comité Ético de Investigación Clínica Parc de Salut MAR (approval No. HCB/2021/0459). All procedures were conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and with Spanish regulations on data protection and patient privacy. Written informed consent was obtained from the caregiver or legal representative of each participant, as patients were unable to provide consent themselves. This trial is registered at ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT02558933).

Additional information

Supplementary Information The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-34576-1>.

Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to V.A.-F.

Reprints and permissions information is available at www.nature.com/reprints.

Publisher's note Springer Nature remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

© The Author(s) 2026